

Some criteria for distinguishing between civil and administrative liability under the legislation of Ukraine

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Objective. The article tries to substantiate once again the truth that the qualitative difference between certain types of offences is an objective reality. It is due to the difference in objective and subjective features, i.e. the nature of objects, subjects, acts, consequences and other features which are characteristic of different types of offences. At the same time, any offence by definition causes harm to specific subjects of social relations. Offences harm social relations defined by law and therefore pose a danger to the stable functioning and development of society.

The methodological basis of the work is a comprehensive analysis of the conceptual framework in administrative law and civil law tortology. The analysis is based on the dialectical method, as well as the analytical method and comparison, which ensure the identification of the essence of phenomena through the characterization of the dynamics

of their development and external manifestations.

Results. The relevance of the study of administrative offences (misdemeanours) and civil law violations is related to the importance of understanding their content, reasons for their commission, and the need to improve current legislation in this area in accordance with current trends in the development of legislation in Ukraine.

Discussion. Apart from its scientific significance and the possibilities of application in the educational process, this article should be noted for its relevance to the law-making and legislative process. The practical significance of the article lies in the fact that it makes it possible to orientate legal doctrine to the needs of practice.

State ment of the problem. When analysing the development of legal regulation of administrative and civil liability institutions in Ukraine, it should be noted that they are characterised by a constant expansion of the range of social relations which require protection by administrative and civil sanctions. The importance in combating of offences is constantly growing.

When describing the essence of administrative and civil liability, the issue of clarifying the peculiarities which distinguish the types of liability becomes of particular importance. This will allow us to consider in more detail the content of administrative and civil liability, its relationship, and to draw a distinction between the one which meets the practical needs of state authorities which detect and

stop of fences and apply appropriate measures of legal liability for the ircommission.

The states tablishesvarious types of legal liability, includ ingtraditional ones, such as criminal, administrative, civil, commercial, financial and disciplinary liability, which exist only within the relevant branches of law.

At the same time, to day in the scientific literature, scholars raise the issue of recognition, establishment and implementation of o the r types of legal liability, such as constitutional, water law, land law, etc. [1,2].

The refore, the issue of distinguishing between administrative and civil liability is relevant and requires additional scientific ly based research.

It is believed that comparison and distinction of the features of the setypes of liability will allow to identify and study the ir peculiarities to the fullest extent possible, which is one of the elements of the subject matter of this article.

The scientific and the oretical basis for the article was provided by scientific works and developments of specialists in the field of administrative and civil law, in particular, V.B. Averyanov, O.M. Bandurka, Y.P. Bytyak, A.S. Vasyliiev, E.S. Gerasymenko, I.P. Golosnichenko, E.V. Dodin, V.V. Zuy, S.V. Kivalov, V.K. Kolpakov, A.T. Komziuk, D.M. Lukianets, O.I. Ostapenko, V.P. Petkov, O.F. Skakun and others.

Key words: administrative liability, responsibility, subject, object, subjective side, objective side, guilt, offence, misdemeanour.

Presentation of the main material. Civil and administrative liability have both similar and distinctive characteristics. The similarities stem from the fact that both belong to the category of legal liability as such. The dif-

ferences, which set them apart, lie in the specific social and legal nature of each of these types of legal liability.

The distinction between civil and administrative liability is important in both theoretical-legal and practical contexts. It is also essential to establish the connections between these types of legal liability.

The identification of common and distinctive characteristics of civil and administrative liability can be addressed through their comparison based on specific elements. In particular, the purpose of administrative liability includes the protection of the rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests of citizens; property and the constitutional order of Ukraine; the rights and legitimate interests of enterprises, institutions, and organizations; the established legal order; the strengthening of legality; the prevention of offenses; and the fostering of citizens' adherence to the Constitution and laws of Ukraine, respect for the honesty and dignity of others, rules of coexistence, conscientious fulfillment of their duties, and responsibility to society [3, p. 204]. Both administrative law scholars [4,5] and civil law scholars [6] agree that a legal violation serves as the basis for both administrative and civil liability. Such a violation has the same structure: an object, an objective side, a subject, and a subjective side. At the same time, there are differences between the characteristics of the elements of administrative offenses (misdemeanors) and civil violations.

For instance, under the Civil Code of Ukraine, civil violations include:

a) Breach of obligation—failure to perform or performance that violates the terms defined by the content of the obligation (improper

performance) by one or both parties to a contract. Examples include breaches of contractual deadlines for fulfilling obligations (delays), failure to perform obligations in kind, loss, shortage, or damage to property, and other material damage caused by non-performance or improper performance of obligations (Chapter 51 of the Civil Code of Ukraine, hereinafter referred to as the Civil Code).

b) Infliction of moral or physical harm (injury, other harm to health, or death) to an individual or legal entity or their property (Chapter 82 of the Civil Code).

In addition to these two main types of civil violations—contractual and non-contractual damage—there are also other types. Despite certain differences between the two main types of civil violations, all of the aforementioned actions share basic common features that allow them to be classified under the same type of legal responsibility.

The general object of a civil violation is the social relations that form the subject of regulation by civil law, namely property relations and personal non-property relations associated with them (Article 1 of the Civil Code), which are based on legal equality, free will, property independence, and broad freedom for participants in determining their rights and obligations. A civil violation occurs within the sphere of private legal interests of individuals and organizations.

An administrative offense (misdemeanor) infringes upon public order, property, the rights and freedoms of citizens, and the established system of governance (Article 9 of the Code of Ukraine on Administrative Offenses). This definition indicates that administrative offenses affect social relations

in various areas of public life, such as labor and health protection, property use, environmental protection, natural resource use, preservation of historical and cultural monuments, maintenance of public order, and others.

The general object of administrative offenses (misdemeanors) is the order of activity in these spheres, established by the state in relevant normative legal acts, meaning it concerns the sphere of public law and national interests. Since some administrative offenses (misdemeanors) not only violate the established state order of activity in certain areas but also may cause harm to citizens and organizations (for example, deceiving a buyer or customer – Article 155-2 of the Code of Ukraine on Administrative Offenses, unfair competition – Article 164-3 of the Code of Ukraine on Administrative Offenses, knowingly false emergency service calls – Article 183 of the Code of Ukraine on Administrative Offenses, etc.), their additional object may be the social relations that are the subject of civil offenses.

It is evident from the above that the objects of the two types of offenses being analyzed pertain to different spheres of social relations. However, the additional object of certain administrative offenses (misdemeanors) may be private legal interests of individuals and organizations, i.e., the sphere of civil offenses.

The objective side of a civil offense is most often expressed in inaction or improper actions, as a result of which moral, physical, or material harm is caused to a natural person, or moral or material harm is caused to a legal entity. The main feature of the objective side of a civil offense is the conse-

quence – the harm caused to a physical or legal person. The amount of harm caused determines the extent of civil liability. The nature of the act resulting in this harm is defined in the law in relatively general terms and does not have significant importance for the type and severity of civil liability measures. An obligatory feature of the objective side of a civil offense is the causal link between the action and the harm caused as a result of this action.

The objective side of an administrative offense (misdemeanor) is formulated differently. It may involve a violation of legally established requirements, rules, or procedures for conducting specific activities (e.g., Articles 41, 50, 78, 92, 122, 203 of the Administrative Offenses Code), or failure to perform actions prescribed by legal acts (e.g., Articles 41-2, 54, 90-1, 122-2 of the Administrative Offenses Code); committing unauthorized actions (self-will) (e.g., Articles 53-1, 60, 70, 97 of the Administrative Offenses Code); or committing specific types of socially dangerous acts (e.g., Articles 42-2, 51, 65-1, 89, etc.).

Most compositions of administrative offenses (misdemeanors) include as part of the objective side the violation, non-fulfillment, or improper fulfillment of rules established by law or subordinate legal acts for the conduct of certain activities. In many cases of administrative offenses (misdemeanors), obligatory features of the objective side include the subject of the unlawful action (e.g., Articles 42-2, 42-3, 51-2, 66, 75 of the Administrative Offenses Code and others), the method (e.g., Articles 65, 72, 82-3, 89, 155-2 of the Administrative Offenses Code), the location (e.g., Articles 173, 174, 179 of the Administrative Offenses Code),

and the circumstances (e.g., Articles 45-1, 58, 59-1, 78, 135 of the Administrative Offenses Code) of the offense.

A distinctive feature of the objective side of administrative offenses (misdemeanors) is that they often do not cause immediate harm but instead create the threat of such harm occurring in the future [7, p. 196].

If an administrative offense (misdemeanor) causes harm to a citizen or an organization, the responsible person may be liable both administratively for the act and civilly for the damage caused.

The interconnection and complementary role of the two types of legal responsibility, discussed here, are legally enshrined in two forms. First, the Administrative Offenses Code (KUpAP) provides for the possibility of imposing the obligation to compensate for minor harm caused by an administrative offense directly within the administrative proceedings (Article 40 KUpAP). In this way, the legislator combines the application of administrative and civil responsibility in such cases. Second, it includes the application of administrative responsibility for the failure to compensate for property damage caused by unlawful actions to enterprises, institutions, organizations, or citizens, by individuals obliged to compensate for such damage under a court verdict or decision (Article 51-1 KUpAP). In this case, administrative responsibility serves as a means to ensure the implementation of civil responsibility.

As a general rule, the subject of a civil offense can be a natural person who has reached the age of 18 (Article 34 of the Civil Code). According to Article 1179 of the Civil Code, the subject of a civil offense related to causing harm may also be a person

aged between 14 and 18 years. Such a person is liable for the damage they caused on general grounds, and if they have no property or income sufficient to compensate for the damage, it must be compensated by their parents (adoptive parents) or guardians if the damage occurred due to their fault.

In addition to reaching a certain age, a mandatory characteristic of the subject of a civil offense is legal capacity, i.e., the ability to acquire civil rights and create civil obligations for oneself. Citizens who, due to mental illness or debility, cannot understand the meaning of their actions or control them, may be declared legally incompetent by the court. Legally incompetent citizens cannot be subjects of civil offenses (Articles 41, 1184 of the Civil Code). Citizens who were capable of legal action but were in a state where they could not understand the significance of their actions or control them at the time of the offense are also not considered subjects of a civil offense, except in cases where they brought themselves into such a state (Article 1186 of the Civil Code).

According to civil legislation, citizens who abuse alcoholic beverages or narcotics and put their family in a difficult financial situation may be restricted by the court in their legal capacity, meaning they may be declared partially legally competent (Article 36 of the Civil Code).

Subjects of civil liability can be both citizens of Ukraine and citizens of other countries or stateless persons. Diplomatic immunity from civil liability is not established, meaning that officials and diplomatic representatives of foreign states can be subjects of civil liability.

In addition to natural persons, subjects of civil liability can also be legal entities

under private and public law—organizations that have separate property and can acquire property and personal non-property rights in their own name, bear obligations, and be plaintiffs or defendants in courts of general jurisdiction, commercial or arbitration courts, including enterprises, institutions, and organizations of all forms of ownership (Articles 80, 92 of the Civil Code). A legal entity can be a proper subject of civil responsibility provided it is legalized and registered in accordance with the established procedure by legal acts. A legal entity is responsible for all types of civil offenses.

In several articles of the Civil Code (CC), responsibility for civil offenses is outlined for special subjects. Specifically, certain special subjects of harm include bodies of state power and local self-government, as well as officials and employees of these bodies (Articles 1172-1175 CC), bodies of inquiry, pre-trial investigation, the prosecutor's office, or courts (Article 1176 CC), and others.

Administrative responsibility for individuals arises two years earlier than civil liability — from the age of 16 (Article 12 of the Administrative Offenses Code, KUpAP). The subject of both administrative and civil responsibility can only be a sane person (Article 20 KUpAP). Foreigners and stateless persons are subject to administrative responsibility on the same grounds as citizens of Ukraine. The question of responsibility for administrative offenses committed by foreigners who, according to applicable laws and international agreements of Ukraine, enjoy immunity from Ukraine's administrative jurisdiction is resolved through diplomatic means (Article 16 KUpAP).

In many administrative offenses (misdemeanors), the subject of the offense has special characteristics, meaning they are specifically defined, as outlined in Article 14 of the General Part of the KUpAP.

Thus, the characteristics of the subjects of civil and administrative liability are quite similar. Some differences in their characteristics are related to the peculiarities of the objective side and the object of both types of offenses.

The subjective characteristics of civil and administrative offenses are also quite similar. Both civil and administrative liability for committing an offense arise only if the person who committed the offense is at fault, either intentionally or through negligence (Articles 614, 1166 of the Civil Code and Articles 9, 10, 11 of the KUpAP). In both codes, fault is a necessary condition for liability. The regulatory provisions regarding the concept of fault and its forms coincide in both codes. The offenses in both civil and administrative law are formulated in such a way that the form of fault and its degree do not affect the severity of the punishment. In some types of civil and administrative offenses, the form of fault (intent or negligence) is directly specified, with the relevant actions being offenses under such conditions (Articles 616, 853, 858, 950 of the Civil Code; Articles 41-1, 46, 46-1, 77, 116, 121, 164-3, 198, 211 of the KUpAP).

At the same time, there are also significant differences in the subjective characteristics of both types of offenses.

First, the content of the offender's fault differs when committing civil and administrative offenses. For civil offenses, it is often characterized by intentional action and neg-

ligent disregard for its consequences. In civil law, a specific type of negligence — gross negligence — is recognized, which is not known in administrative law. Gross negligence is directly provided as a necessary element in certain types of civil offenses (Articles 337, 340, 950, 1193 of the Civil Code).

Another feature of fault in civil offenses is the consideration of the victim's fault in causing the offense. Given the equality of the subjects of civil relations and their nature, this situation is quite natural.

A significant feature of civil offenses is the possibility of committing certain types of offenses without fault. An example of this is causing harm with a source of increased danger (Article 1187 of the Civil Code). An organization or individual using a source of increased danger is responsible for any harm caused, except in cases of force majeure or intentional actions by the victim.

It is important to point out the circumstances that exclude liability in the case of civil and administrative offenses. Committing an offense (misdemeanor) in a state of necessary defense, provided that its limits were not exceeded, excludes both civil and administrative liability (Article 1169 of the Civil Code and Article 19 of the Code of Administrative Offenses).

Committing an offense in a state of extreme necessity excludes administrative liability if it allowed for the elimination of a danger that could not have been removed by other means under the given circumstances, and if the harm caused is less significant than the harm that was prevented (Article 18 of the Code of Administrative Offenses).

Committing a civil offense in a state of extreme necessity, as a general rule, does not relieve the person who committed it from liability. In certain cases, the court, considering the circumstances of the case, may impose the obligation to compensate for the damage caused in such a state on the person in whose interest the harmful act was performed, or oblige both parties to compensate the damage in certain shares, or relieve them from compensating for the damage either partially or in full (Article 1171 of the Civil Code).

Being in a state of insanity excludes administrative liability (Article 20 of the Code of Administrative Offenses). Committing a civil offense by a person recognized as legally incompetent excludes their liability but entails the liability of their guardian or the organization responsible for supervising them, if the latter cannot prove that the harm was not caused by their fault (Article 1184 of the Civil Code).

Thus, despite the similarities in the basic features of the subjective side of civil and administrative offenses (misdemeanors), there are significant differences between them. For an administrative offense (misdemeanor), the predominant importance lies in the offender's mental attitude towards the act they have committed, while for a civil offense, it is related to the consequences of the aforementioned act. A civil offense may be committed due to a specific type of negligence, gross negligence, which is not provided for in specific administrative offense compositions.

A feature of administrative responsibility is the presence of circumstances that mitigate or aggravate responsibility for an adminis-

trative offense (Articles 34 and 35 of the Code of Administrative Offenses). Such circumstances are defined by the law as certain objective and subjective characteristics of the administrative offense (misdemeanor). Notably, one such feature is the prevention of harmful consequences of the offense by the offender, voluntary compensation for the damage, or the removal of the harm caused, i.e., the socially dangerous consequences characteristic of civil offenses.

Therefore, administrative and civil liability are distinct from each other. They are clearly differentiated by all distinguishing features. In theory and practice, there are no issues regarding potential duplication or competition between these types of legal liability. At the same time, each type of liability serves its own specific function. When both administrative and civil liability are applied, they complement each other, contributing to more effective maintenance of law and order in Ukraine.

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Ukrayna qanunvericiliyinə əsasən mülki və inzibati məsuliyyəti ayırd etmək üçün bəzi meyarlar

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Məqsəd. Məqalədə ayrı-ayrı hüquqpozma növləri arasında keyfiyyət fərqlinin obyektiv reallıq olması həqiqəti bir daha əsaslandırılmağa çalışılır. Bu, obyektiv və subyektiv əlamətlərin, yəni müxtəlif növ cinayətlərə xas olan obyektlərin, subyektlərin, hərəkətlərin, nəticələrin və digər əlamətlərin xarakteri ilə əlaqədardır. Eyni zamanda, hər hansı bir cinayət tərifinə görə ictimai münasibətlərin konkret subyektlərinə zərər vurur. Hüquq pozuntuları qanunla müəyyən edilmiş ictimai münasibətlərə xələl gətirir və buna görə də, cəmiyyətin sabit fəaliyyətinə və inkişafına təhlükə yaradır.

Açar sözlər: inzibati məsuliyyət, məsuliyyət, subyekt, obyekt, subyektiv tərəf, obyektiv tərəf, təqsir, hüquq pozuntusu, cinayət.

Ukrayna mevzuatına görə medeni və idari sorumluluk arasında ayırım yapmaya yönelik bazı kriterler

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Nesnel. Makale, belirli suç türleri arasındaki niteliksel farklılığın nesnel bir gerçeklik olduğu gerçeğini bir kez daha kanıtlamaya çalışmaktadır. Bu, nesnel ve öznel özelliklerdeki farktan, yani farklı suç türlerinin karakteristiği olan nesnelere, öznelere, eylemlerin, sonuçların ve diğer özelliklerin doğasından kaynaklanmaktadır. Aynı zamanda, herhangi bir suç tanımı gereği toplumsal ilişkilerin belirli öznelere zarar verir. Suçlar, kanunla tanımlanan toplumsal ilişkilere zarar verir ve bu nedenle toplumun istikrarlı işleyişi ve gelişimi için bir tehlike oluşturur.

Anahtar Sözcükler: idari sorumluluk, sorumluluk, konu, nesne, öznel taraf, nesnel taraf, suçluluk, suç, kabahat.

